

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.7905 Max: 63.0073	1396 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #:	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION Tufo floor Room No 6	Covered by KSU: 1327	Fills SU:	Filled by SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)	Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1327	Covers: 1417 (wall below 1396), (2nd floor)
Is cut by: 1347,	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: (Room)

OBSERVATIONS
Excavation began after hard rain night before. Floor removed by pickaxe and trowel

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: Southern corner on western side, south-west corner
Shape: Floor condition degraded, therefore shape is very irregular and patchy

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): Slopes slightly (very slightly) west
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Tufo stones of varying sizes (Range from 12-2cm, all irregular) shapes & sizes
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): constant
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

<p>For cuts complete this section:</p> <p>Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight</p> <p>Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping</p> <p>Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular</p> <p>How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded</p> <p>How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded</p> <p>Observations:</p>	<p>Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):</p>
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For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: *Fills Room N°6*

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify) *crushed tufo floor*

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains: *longest measurements ~190cm x 310*

Description:

Irregular and patchy preservation of tufo floor, distinguished by rich orange stone

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

see front

INTERPRETATION

*Patchy floor of crushed tufo that is suggested to span Room N°6. (which is bound by walls 1390, 1391, 1392, 1393. Wall remains below 1396 show another occupation layer below this floor. Also another tufo floor shows earlier occupation (indicated by * on drawing). These earlier remains indicate multiple building phases in Room N°6.*

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by <i>AMB</i>	on <i>20.07.2011</i>
Revised by <i>CHM</i>	on <i>20.07.2011</i>
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Entered by	on